

AiRT

TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER OF REMOTELY PILOTED AIRCRAFT SYSTEMS (RPAS) FOR THE CREATIVE INDUSTRY

THE INDOOR DRONE FOR CREATIVE AGENCIES

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